

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE IMPACT OF MEDIA INFORMATION FLOWS AND PR CAMPAIGNS ON TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

Tourism plays a crucial role in international economic relations and is an integral part of the global economic development. Georgia, with its rich cultural heritage, unique nature, and historical significance, is a distinguished tourist destination. During the Soviet era, the country had an extensive network of mass tourism, resort treatments, and recreational facilities, and after independence, it quickly became a rapidly growing tourist destination. In the 21st century, as the world became more interconnected through digital media, the impact of media communication phenomena on the tourism industry reached unprecedented heights. Information spreading rapidly in the digital landscape is critical for shaping perception and attracting tourists. Positive information flows can strengthen Georgia's image as a tourist and culturally rich country. Conversely, negative information can deter potential tourists.

Research in Georgia on media communication has primarily focused on political or social phenomena, and informational (PR) campaigns in the tourism sector have never been a subject of special research, and thus, analysis and evaluation. The present study examined PR campaigns conducted by Georgia's tourism sector between 2019-2023 and their impact on tourist inflows, highlighting factors influencing Polish tourists' perceptions of Georgia. Using mixed methods (narrative and quantitative content analysis, comparative analysis, case study), it studied tourist inflows during the reporting period, PR materials, articles, blogs, posts, and other social media content about Georgia.

The findings indicate that the strategic marketing and PR efforts implemented, especially through digital media, significantly increased the visibility and attractiveness of Georgia as a tourist destination, contributing to substantial growth in tourism revenues and international visitors. The research emphasizes the significant contribution of media campaigns in portraying a positive image of Georgia. Intensive marketing and PR campaigns implemented after the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic led to a noticeable increase in the number of international tourists and tourism revenues, as evidenced by the analysis of economic indicators, highlighting the sector's resilience and its critical role in the national economy.

The study concludes with recommendations for maintaining and increasing Georgia's growth as a top tourist destination, emphasizing the need for digital marketing, targeted marketing campaigns, and investments in tourism infrastructure and services. These initiatives are crucial for maintaining Georgia's competitive advantage in the global tourism market and ensuring sustainable development.

Keywords: Georgia's tourism, Media communication, Media information flows, PR campaigns, Polish tourists' perception of Georgia

Introduction

Tourism is an integral part of international economic relations and a significant lever for global economic development. Its role and importance are continuously increasing. In the 21st century, in the era of globalization, tourism has evolved into a sector of sus-

tainable development for world culture and the economy, securing a special place in the global economic structure.

Tourism has always been popular in Georgia. During the Soviet period, it included an extensive network of mass tourism, health resorts, and recreational facilities. Since gaining independence, the tourism industry in Georgia has become one of the most important and

rapidly growing sectors. Known as a Silk Road country and a crossroads of Europe and Asia, Georgia attracts visitors with its unique nature, rich and distinctive culture (including music, dance, art, history, religion, and numerous cultural heritage sites of both international and local significance, among which three are listed in UNESCO's "World Heritage List"), favorable climatic conditions, 87 protected areas including 11 national parks, ancient winemaking traditions, and excellent gastronomy. Additionally, the friendly attitude and hospitality of the Georgian people make it appealing to visitors.

International travel significantly contributes to global economic development. According to the World Travel & Tourism Council (WTTC), in 2021, the direct contribution of this sector to the world's GDP was \$5.8 trillion (+21.7%), supporting the creation of 289 million jobs. Considering its direct and indirect effects, the sector's contribution to global economic development includes 6.1% of the world's GDP, accounting for one in every 11 jobs.

Tourism plays a crucial role in Georgia's economy. According to statistical data, in 2019, tourism revenues exceeded \$3.3 billion, accounting for 8.1% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). However, these figures dropped sharply due to COVID-19.

Current, revenues from tourism amount to \$1.9 billion, contributing 7.2% directly to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). It is projected to grow to 7.9% in the near future.

Attracting visitors from high-spending markets is a key goal of Georgia's tourism strategy, [2] achievable through effective marketing and informational (PR) campaigns. In the information society, people's social interest in information holds deep practical significance and implies the public context in which information generation, processing, and transmission become primary sources of productivity (M. Castells). [3]

According to the World Tourism Organization (Citation2018), 93% of internet users search for travel-related information. Tourists use multi-platform media sites to seek travel information. [4] Consequently, this information search influences their decisions to plan, undertake, and evaluate trips. [5] In modern tourism, the internet is strategically important for developing countries as it helps create a competitive space and develop the tourism market. Like the rest of the world, Georgia follows new trends and mainly disseminates media information flows in digital format. In this landscape, rapidly spreading information is crucial for shaping perceptions and attracting tourists. Positive information flows can strengthen Georgia's image as a tourist destination and a culturally rich country. Conversely, negative information can deter potential tourists.

This drives the research interest in how media information flows affect tourists' perceptions of Georgia as a tourist destination; how PR campaigns shape Georgia's image in the global tourism market; and what key factors determine the success of PR campaigns in attracting tourists to Georgia.

Since 2010, the National Tourism Administration has been directing tourism development policy in Georgia. Therefore, the aim of this research was to determine the effectiveness of the informational (PR) campaigns conducted by the National Tourism Administration during the years 2019-2023 and to identify key factors that contribute to the success of media information flows and PR campaigns in attracting tourists to Georgia. The research employed mixed methods: narrative and quantitative content analysis, comparative analysis, and case study. The selection of media articles, blogs, posts, other social media content, and PR materials about Georgia published from 2019-2023 was based on relevance, accessibility, and impact. Content analysis processed the media content about Georgia disseminated during the reporting period (media sources, discourse, messages, themes, etc.). Using the case study method, PR events (including tours, visits, exhibitions) were analyzed on both national and international platforms. In evaluating PR campaigns, direct indicators included tourism revenue and visitor statistics. Accordingly, a comparative analysis reviewed data from the National Tourism Administration and the National Statistics Office. Along with measuring the effectiveness of PR campaigns in the media, key factors influencing European tourists' decisions to travel to Georgia were studied using Poland as an example. This part of the research evaluated materials published in both traditional and social media, traveler feedback, and responses. Poland was chosen considering its strategic importance identified by the National Tourism Administration—Poland and Germany are key target groups for Georgia in the coming years.

Main Text

Georgia on Global Multiplatform Channels. The National Tourism Administration of Georgia conducted marketing campaigns in target markets during 2019-2023 based on three criteria; Direct air access, Assessment of countries' interest, Spending capacity of countries. These campaigns were diverse and included: Digital and broadcast media advertisements and participation in programs; Press and info tours: hosting journalists, bloggers, influencers, and tour operators in the country;

Participation in international exhibitions, such as ITB Berlin, exhibitions in London, Madrid, New York, Paris, and India, where both the public and private sectors of tourism were collectively represented.

A notable digital project in these campaigns is the www.Georgia.travel [6], portal, which hosts around 3,200 articles in English about significant attractions and tourism products. Visitors can plan their desired route and travel by train, bus, minibus, and other transport. The website is fully adapted for people with disabilities. To increase international visits to Georgia, a strategic goal of the Georgian National Tourism Administration is to raise awareness about Georgia. In 2019, the National Tourism Administration participated in 30 international tourism exhibitions, conducted 131 press and info tours (hosting 574 journalists, bloggers, film crews, and 257 tour

operators). As a result of the press tours, around 300 articles, posts, and blogs were prepared; about 15 TV programs and segments were produced; and presentations showcasing Georgia as an attractive tourist destination were held in several countries: Japan, Uzbekistan, Czech Republic, Israel, Spain, and Korea. [7] In 2020-2021, the number of tourists in Georgia, as well as worldwide, decreased unprecedentedly due to the pandemic. According to the World Tourism Organization, global international tourism revenues decreased by one billion, equating to a -74% decline, reaching the levels recorded in 1990. In 2022, 54 press tours were conducted in Georgia with the participation of 482 individuals, including TV crew members, journalists, bloggers, influencers, and photographers. Additionally, 8 info tours were organized with 58 participants. Notably, the travels of Canadian photographers to various tourist destinations stood out. Their photographic works, showcasing places like Ushguli, Gudauri, Tbilisi, and other tourist attractions, were displayed to passengers at Toronto International Airport for two months. [8]

In the same year, a promotional video about Georgia's tourism potential was recognized as the best clip in the European region. The video titled "Guest" won in the UN World Tourism Organization's nomination "Tourism and the Decade of Action." The winning tourist destinations were selected by a jury composed of media professionals. [9] Highlights of that year's projects included articles about Georgia published on Bloomberg as part of a campaign, and the dissemination of videos through digital marketing on social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, and TikTok. In terms of planned and implemented PR campaigns, 2023 was significantly more active. The National Tourism Administration conducted marketing campaigns on major international platforms such as Bloomberg, Expedia, Skyscanner, and the Willy Scharnow Foundation for Tourism. Georgia's tourism products were showcased at exhibitions in London, Warsaw, Paris, Helsinki, Milan, Dubai, Riga, Tel Aviv, Madrid, and Berlin. The campaigns included social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube. [10]

The PR campaigns encompassed 67 informational and 13 familiarization tours from the following countries: the Baltic States, USA, Slovenia, Germany, Austria, South Korea, Hungary, Czech Republic, Azerbaijan, Italy, Greece, France, Spain, Great Britain, Qatar, Uzbekistan, United Arab Emirates, Sweden, Israel, Iran, and India, Canada, Belgium, Bulgaria, Saudi Arabia, Armenia, and Kazakhstan.

254 individuals participated in the tours (TV crew members, journalists, bloggers, influencers, and photographers). Articles, blogs, stories, and video clips about the country's tourism potential were prepared by influential media outlets such as: The Guardian, Forbes, The Financial Times, Elle, The Times, Marie-Claire, National Geographic, Saveur, Vogue, The

Sunday Times, The Telegraph, GQ, Die Presse, Snow, Backcountry Magazine, The Huffington Post, Le Figaro, [11] Sueddeutsche Zeitung, [12] and others. Within these campaigns, 23 articles were published, segments were aired on 9 TV programs, and around 100 posts and stories were shared on social media. [13]

Among the notable activities was the promotion of various regions of Georgia at the international exhibition "TT Warsaw 2023", where 247 tourism companies from 50 countries received information about the tourism products of Adjara, Imereti, Samegrelo, and Svaneti. [14] It is noteworthy that in 2023, Tbilisi was included in CNN's list of Christmas travel cities for the first time, featuring among cities from Austria, Germany, Poland, Norway, Belgium, France, and the Netherlands. [15] Tbilisi was also featured in a comprehensive article by the influential travel publication "Conde Nast Traveler," which covered Christmas preparations in popular cities such as London, Berlin, Bern, Edinburgh, Bruges, Copenhagen, Dubai, Hong Kong, New York, and Montreal. [16]

Additionally, the first digital conference, TRAVERSE, [17] was held in Georgia. During the event, the country hosted about 180 influencers from the UK, USA, Germany, Poland, Spain, France, and other countries. During the digital TRAVERSE, the influencers traveled to Tbilisi, Mestia, and Gudauri, where they explored resorts, tourist products, Georgian cuisine, and wines. This campaign significantly contributed to the promotion of Georgia.

The study of media content reveals that the informational campaigns conducted by the National Tourism Administration significantly contribute to promoting a positive image of Georgia. These campaigns often highlight the country's unique opportunities in the tourism sector, the colorful blend of European and Asian subcultures, and emphasize Georgia's unique cultural richness, natural beauty, and historical significance. They also showcase the ancient institution of hospitality and the country's excellent gastronomy.

Local Tourism Trend

In evaluating the PR campaigns conducted by the National Tourism Administration, direct indicators include revenues and statistics. A relevant measure of a country's tourism sector development is the number of international tourists. In 2019, the number of international traveler visits was 9,357,964. It decreased in 2022 to 5,426,903, but in 2023, the number of international traveler visits is 7,072,220, which shows a positive increase compared to the previous year's data (+30.3%). See Table N1. However, the revenues of 2023 exceeded those of 2019.

	2019	2022	2023	Change 2019/2023	Change 2022/2023	change 2019/2023 %	change 2022/2023 %
international travelers' visits	9 357 964	5 426 903	7 072 220	-2 285 744	1 645 317	-24,4%	30,3%
other visits (non-touristic)"	1 632 190	722 958	900 680	-731 510	177 722	-44,8%	24,6%
"visits carried out by international visitors"	7 725 774	4 703 945	6 171 540	-1 554 234	1 467 595	-20,1%	31,2%

Source: Compiled by the authors based on data from the National Statistics Office of Georgia.

Diagram 1. Number of International Tourists in Georgia from 2013 to 2023

Diagram 1. Visits by Non-Resident Visitors to Georgia from 2013 to 2023

Source: Compiled by the authors based on data from the National Statistics Office of Georgia.

Table 2. Visits by International Visitors from the Top 15 Countries

Country	2019	2022	2023	Change 2019/2023	Change 2022/2023	Change 2019/2023 %	change 2022/2023 %
Turkey	1 156 513	925 561	1 396 660	240 147	471 099	20,8%	50,9%
Russion	1 471 558	1 087 257	1 418 464	-53 094	331 207	-3,6%	30,5%
Armenia	1 365 048	742 593	962 540	-402 508	219 947	-29,5%	29,6%
Israel	205 051	210 178	217 065	12 014	6 887	5,9%	3,3%
Azerbaijan	1 526 619	152 969	199 835	-1 326 784	46 866	-86,9%	30,6%
Kazakhstan	103 611	120 494	167 492	63 881	46 998	61,7%	39,0%
Ukraine	207 667	168 915	146 931	-60 736	-21 984	-29,2%	-13,0%
Iran	141 997	102 877	126 282	-15 715	23 405	-11,1%	22,8%
Belarus	66 174	130 046	130 203	64 029	157	96,8%	0,1%
Poland	88 300	41 917	91 210	2 910	49 293	3,3%	117,6%
India	54 606	52 841	84 688	30 082	31 847	55,1%	60,3%
Germany	89 051	48 548	68 824	-20 227	20 276	-22,7%	41,8%
უზბეკეთი	16 785	47 953	52 088	35 303	4 135	210,3%	8,6%

ამერიკის შეერთებული შტატები	46 558	35 319	43 654	-2 904	8 335	-6,2%	23,6%
საუდის არაბეთი	75 155	119 921	74 318	-837	-45 603	-1,1%	-38,0%

Source: Compiled by the authors based on data from the National Statistics Office of Georgia.

In 2023, the highest number of international visits within the year was recorded in the third quarter, totaling 2,706,873. During this period, the number of visits increased by 19.4% compared to the total international visits recorded in 2022. The first quarter had the lowest number of visits at 1,203,462. Diagram 3 depicts visits by international visitors from the top 15 countries in 2023.

Diagram 2. Visits by International Visitors in 2023

Source: Compiled by the authors based on data from the National Statistics Office of Georgia.

Diagram N3. Visits by International Visitors from the Top 15 Countries

Source: Compiled by the authors based on data from the National Statistics Office of Georgia.

According to the 2022 statistical report, revenue from foreign travel to Georgia amounted to \$1.24 billion (an increase of +129.8%, recovering 38.1% of the 2019 level), and the total added value amounted to 3.38

billion GEL due to increased demand (an increase of +32.3%).

Diagram N4. Revenue from Foreign Travel to Georgia

According to statistics, in 2023, 7.72 million international travelers visited, of which 4.669 million were international tourist visits (91% recovery compared to 2019). There was a 27% increase in tourist flows compared to 2022. In 2023, tourism revenue reached 4.1 billion USD (a 26% increase compared to 2019). The top countries in 2022-2023 showing growth, where various marketing activities were conducted, include Poland, Germany, India, Saudi Arabia, Kazakhstan, Israel, and China. According to Master Card data, the most demanded products were local cuisine and wine, culture, and adventure activities, which is a direct effect of the events held. It should also be noted that the number of overnight stays significantly increased to 5.4 nights (a 31% increase compared to 2019).

The factors influencing Polish perceptions of Georgia and its attractiveness as a tourist destination

The perception of Georgia, as a country at the crossroads of Europe and Asia, in Poland is shaped primarily by the media, the traditional ones - radio and television, but above all the electronic ones. However, there is also a shortage of books - reportages Gaumar-dzós! Tales from Georgia [18] - A. Dziewit-Meller and M. Meller, Georgia. Jak się żyje Polce w kraju wina, gościnności i drogowych absurdów - M. Kaczmarzyk (2021). [19] And many guidebook titles on the country.

Georgia is described by those who have visited it many times. Many accounts are written of journeys through the picturesque and captivating country. Most often, they are posted on the web as travel blogs and travel websites, providing a source of information about Georgia's qualities for potential tourists. In the virtual space, portals such as bartekwpodrozy.pl, paragonzpodrozy.pl/ zblogowani.pl, blogipodróznicze.pl, solisci.pl or globetrotters' websites such as: odysei.com, globtroter.pl, geoblog.pl and tubyliśmy.pl provide not only descriptions of trips, but also accounts

with rich, captivating photographic documentation. [20] Travel-themed posts can be found on social media (Facebook, Instagram). The interest of media celebrities [21] recommending Georgia also contributes to the choice of this destination as a holiday destination. Consequently, Georgia is becoming a travel and leisure destination more and more eagerly chosen by Poles every year.

According to the World Tourism Organisation's data on package holidays, Poles accounted for 2 per cent (5,000 people) in 2010 and 3 per cent (44,000) of all tourists visiting Georgia in 2021. This places Poles in tenth place in terms of the number of tourist arrivals, by nationality. The cited data shows that the number of Polish tourists in Georgia has increased almost nine times over the decade. [22]

A question arises about the image of Georgia, shaped by the media, which consequently leads to a dynamically growing interest in the country. In the Polish popular perception, Georgia is characterised by its multifaceted attractiveness, which is why many tourists, with different interests and expectations, are confident that they will be able to find something for themselves. Georgia has many faces, so those who seek proximity to unspoiled, untouched nature will find it in the Caucasus Mountains. Those captivated by history, dating back to the 2nd millennium B.C., with its monuments, such as the medieval museum city of Mtskheta, will also find a wealth of impressions. Those looking for an exotic holiday will find it in Batumi, on the Black Sea coast, where the subtropical climate allows Mediterranean plants to thrive. Batumi, is seen as a place that guarantees pleasant, moderate temperatures even in December, which can be an escape from the capricious winter in Poland. Supporters of holidays in the south of Europe, find in Batumi a city that combines the best of Georgia with what is oriental in Turkey. [23]

For the Polish tourist, the most important criterion for choosing a holiday destination is its cost. Consequently, one of the reasons for the dynamic growth of interest in Georgia is the launch of direct connections of low-cost airlines, widely advertised in social media and outdoor advertising. The launch of connections from Katowice, one of the largest Polish urban areas, to Kutaisi or Batumi, among others, means that Georgia, with a flight lasting about 3.5 hours, is practically within reach for the average Pole.

Georgia's popularity is also determined by the relatively low cost of stay, hotel rentals, transfers between attractions, restaurants and others. The aspect of relatively low expenses related to holidays in Georgia is also raised in the public space and constitutes a significant element attracting Polish tourists there.

Since 2008, there has been a continuous increase in Polish awareness of Georgia's pro-European aspirations has been growing, which can most often be heard

about on public television. There, the public protests of June 2022, when the EU denied Georgia the status of candidate country, were widely and positively commented on. In this context, it is also worth highlighting the importance of Georgia being perceived as a country with a stabilising economic, political situation. This is fostered by the process of deepening integration with the European Union, reinforced by the status of an official candidate from December 2023. The political context, particularly close to the Poles, is related to the presidency of L. Kaczyński, when there was a clear rapprochement between Poland and Georgia, strengthened by the personal contacts of the then presidents. This undoubtedly contributed to creating a positive image of Georgia in the Polish media and emphasising the ties between the two countries. Poles know that the importance of Polish-Georgian contacts can be seen in many places in Georgia, in the names of streets (Tbilisi), squares (Batumi), and commemorative plaques (Gori).

Visits of Polish tourists to Georgia are, apart from forms of organized tourism, the participants of which are usually mature people, they are carried out by young people, often students with a limited budget, but with a significant influence in the network. Young people's trips include backpacking, hitchhiking, cycling, combined with mountain exploration, all forms of active tourism.

When examining the advantages of Georgia that are highlighted in public discourse, its investment attractiveness is increasingly being pointed out. [24] The official government website (gov.pl/) contains an information guide for potential investors from Poland. Publications referring to the World Bank's Doing Business report, pointing to Georgia's 7th position in the above-mentioned ranking (Poland 40th out of 190 countries) [25]. In terms of the ease of starting a business, Georgia ranks 2nd in the world and 5th in the world for registering real estate, which makes Polish entrepreneurs more willing to locate their investments in this country. This regulatory environment is conducive to starting and running a local business. The interest of Polish business in the Georgian market is reflected [26], among others, in investment forums. An example of this was the Polish-Georgian Investment Forum "Invest on Georgia" held in Telavi on October 18-19, 2022. The event was organized by the Polish Ministry of Funds and Regional Policy (MFIPR) together with the Ministry of Regional Development and Infrastructure of Georgia and the Kakheti Region as part of the project entitled "Increase in the competitiveness of Georgian regions and development of entrepreneurship [27]."

To summarize, Poles are drawn to visit the country of Georgia for a variety of reasons, including:

- The cultural richness: Georgia has a long history and culture that dates back thousands of years. Visitors are attracted to its unique architecture, traditional music, clothing dance, and art.
- The hospitality: Georgians are known for their hospitality and welcoming attitude towards guests. The concept of "supra," or traditional Georgian feast, is a central part of Georgian culture where guests are treated with utmost respect and generosity.

- The natural beauty: When thinking about Georgia, it is impossible not to mention nature, because this country is full of nature, delighting everyone who has ever visited it. Georgia boasts diverse landscapes, including the stunning Caucasus Mountains, green valleys, and the Black Sea coastline. It offers opportunities for hiking, skiing, and exploring picturesque countryside. There are 12 national parks in Georgia, but the entire country can be considered a natural gem. The Caucasus is an ideal place for fans of trekking or climbing at lower and higher altitudes.

- Wine and Cuisine: Georgia is one of the oldest wine-producing regions in the world, with a winemaking tradition that spans over 8,000 years [28]. Visitors can enjoy tasting unique Georgian wines and sampling the delicious local cuisine, which features dishes like khachapuri (cheese-filled bread) and khinkali (dumplings). Georgia is the land of the best wines, both sweet and slightly more dry. The Kakheti region is particularly touted, along with the city of Telavi, where you can also see the remains of the oldest preserved wine in the history of the world.

- Historical Sites: Georgia is seen as a home to numerous historical sites and monuments, including ancient churches, fortresses, and cave cities. Prominent landmarks such as the medieval town of Mtskheta and the cave monastery of Vardzia attract history enthusiasts from around the world.

- The affordability: Compared to many other European destinations, Georgia offers relatively affordable travel options, including accommodations, dining, and transportation.

- The adventure Tourism: Georgia provides opportunities for adventure enthusiasts, with activities such as trekking, mountain biking, whitewater rafting, and paragliding available in various regions of the country.

- Economic opportunities- according to Doing Business Georgia was ranked at the 7th place in the world. This the regulatory environment is more conducive to the starting and operation of a local firm. Moreover according to starting business is ranked at 2th place and registering property at 5th place.

Georgia has many faces. In fact, no trip can discover each of them. Each time Georgia will be different, depending on the season, region and even the means of transport we will use. One of the descriptions found on the Internet characterizes Georgia as follows: "Georgia's attractions are full of contrasts - snow-capped peaks and sandy beaches, developed agglomerations teeming with life and small settlements where time has stopped. It's a country with hospitality you won't find anywhere else." After such a recommendation, there is nothing left to do but look for the first flight connection to get to Tbilisi as soon as possible and start a charming journey around the country at the crossroads of continents and cultures. Overall, Georgian tourism has promising prospects. There is a large and still untapped potential in it. As above has been mentioned, the natural, historical and cultural values are appreciated by Poles, and this destination for foreign travel is increasingly chosen by them. Georgia offers a

unique blend of culture, history, natural beauty, and hospitality, making it an appealing destination for travelers seeking authentic experiences.

Conclusion

The Georgian National Tourism Administration effectively utilized strategic marketing campaigns in 2022-2023 to elevate the country's status as a tourist destination. Their diverse and well-planned efforts not only increased global awareness but also established a strong foundation for sustained growth, even amid global challenges such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Through continuous adaptation and proactive measures, especially using influential media and digital platforms, Georgia is effectively positioned for a sustainable increase in international tourist numbers.

It is noteworthy that, 20 years ago, the country did not conduct any marketing or informational campaigns. Today, Georgia's tourism industry competes with some of the world's most established destinations. By strategically disseminating media information, Georgia has significantly raised its profile. Key initiatives, such as creating comprehensive web portals like Georgia.travel and places.georgia.travel, and implementing other targeted digital marketing projects, are crucial for long-term perspectives. These initiatives, combined with extensive media coverage and engaging content on social media platforms, have significantly increased Georgia's visibility and attractiveness.

The production of promotional videos has played a crucial role in making Georgia more accessible and appealing to international tourists. Despite setbacks during the pandemic, the administration's PR efforts led to a strong increase in tourist arrivals in 2022 and 2023.

In Poland, as in other countries, various media, especially electronic platforms, significantly influence perceptions of Georgia. Although there is a shortage of books on this topic, numerous travel blogs, social media posts, and online travel guides provide potential tourists with information about Georgia's unique opportunities, enhancing its popularity among Polish tourists. The diverse media portrayal has resulted in a substantial increase in Polish tourists visiting Georgia, nearly nine times higher from 2010 to 2021.

Recommendations:

Digital Marketing and Diverse Content Creation: Building on the success of strategic marketing campaigns, Georgia should continue to innovate and expand its digital marketing efforts. This includes creating high-quality, engaging content such as virtual tours, interactive maps, and personalized travel itineraries on platforms like Georgia.travel. Collaborating with popular travel influencers and bloggers to create authentic travel stories and experiences can further enhance Georgia's visibility and appeal.

Targeted Marketing Campaigns for Different Audiences: Marketing efforts should be tailored to different segments of tourists, such as adventure seekers, cultural enthusiasts, and high-budget travelers. It is also essential to use data analytics to understand the preferences of various tourist demographics, which will help in developing more effective and appealing campaigns.

Strengthening Tourist Infrastructure and Services: To ensure a high-quality experience for high-spending visitors, continuous investment in tourist infrastructure is necessary. This includes improving transportation links, accommodation options, and tourist attractions, particularly in less developed regions. Training programs for local service providers to enhance hospitality and customer service skills will contribute to better tourist experiences. Additionally, establishing information centers at major tourist locations and providing multilingual support will help tourists navigate and enjoy their travels in Georgia more effectively.

By implementing these recommendations, Georgia can maintain and strengthen its growth as a premier tourist destination, ensuring competitiveness with other top global destinations.

References

1. "Georgian National Tourism Administration. International Visitors Research, 2022."
2. "Georgia Tourism Strategy 2025".
3. Informationism and network society. <http://socium.ge/index.php/socium-ge-library/tanamedrove2/99939-informacional-izmi-qseluri-sazogadoeba>
4. (Abbasi et al., Citation2023; Jamshidi et al., Citation2023).
5. Jacobsen & Munar, Citation2012.
6. <https://georgia.travel/>
7. https://gnta.ge/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/2019_GEO_PRINT.pdf
8. Note: Toronto International Airport is one of the busiest in the world, with 36 million passengers expected in 2022.
9. <https://www.facebook.com/georgi-aandtravel/videos/868273827685269>
10. <https://sponsored.bloomberg.com/article/a-food-filled-adventure-through-georgia>
11. <https://www.lefigaro.fr/>
12. <https://gnta.ge/ge/le-figaro-the-telegraph-gq/>
13. <https://gnta.ge/ge/international-media-gnta/>
14. <https://gnta.ge/ge/tt-warsaw-2023/>
15. <https://www.neventum.com/tradeshows/tt-warsaw>
16. <https://edition.cnn.com/travel/european-towns-and-cities-that-look-like-christmas/index.html>
17. <https://www.cntraveler.com/galleries/2015-12-08/copenhagen-to-quebec-14-cities-that-do-christmas-best?fbclid=IwAR1QqRFagKxr80GnFsc9NTPyW1WY9OLJNxHicjkt6rVVNCfbbIUGA41Bg>
18. <https://gnta.ge/ge/traverse-in-georgia/>
19. Tales from Georgia A. Dziewit-Meller and M. Meller (2018)

20. Georgia. Jak się żyje Polce w kraju wina, gościnności i drogowych absurdów - M. Kaczmarzyk (2021).
21. E.Szczepkowska, O https://repozytorium.uwb.edu.pl/jspui/bitstream/11320/15195/1/E_Szczepkowska
22. kobieta.interia.pl/gwiazdy
23. <https://www.unwto.org/tourism-data/global-and-regional-tourism-performance>
24. wydarzenia.interia.pl/zagranica/news
25. www.gov.pl/web/gruzja/informator-ekonomiczn
26. <https://archive.doingbusiness.org/en/rankings>
27. State-of-Play.-Poland-Georgia.pdf
28. <https://www.trade.gov.pl/kalendarz/polsko-gruzinskie-forum-inwestycyjne-invest-in-georgia>
29. wydarzenia.interia.pl/zagranica/news-polacy-oblegaja-ten-wakacyjny-kierunek-jest-pieknie-cieplo